

Probing Dynamical Activity of Sgr A* using VLBI Closure Quantities

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Abstract

Sagittarius A* is the name given to the compact radio source at the center of the Milky Way. In 1994 Narayan et al. noted that the source exhibited relatively low luminosity for the large amount of mass it was accreting. They posited that this could be resolved with the black hole model for accretion in which most of the energy was absorbed by the black hole rather than being released as radiation. In 1998, using the Keck 10m telescope to measure the proper motion of stars around the galactic core, Ghez et al. were able to determine constraints for size and mass of the object that aligned with the characteristics of a massive black hole. With more refined calculations, these key observations amongst others provide strong evidence to suggest Sagittarius A* is a supermassive black hole. Given its relative proximity and mass, Sgr A* has the largest angular event horizon of any black hole, making it ideal for further analysis. Millimeter VLBI observations of Sgr A* performed with the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) demonstrate the existence of structural variation on timescales that correspond to the Schwarzschild radius. The ability to resolve both the spatial and temporal structures on event horizon scales suggests many applications for testing General Relativity in very strong gravitation fields. In preparation for higher-resolution sub-millimeter VLBI data coming in the next 6 months, we explore closure amplitude and phase signatures of simulated GRMHD movies. These valuable plots allow us to determine important values such as Sag A*'s angle of orientation and the amount of accreted matter there is around. By synthesizing and analyzing data ahead of time, we will be more apt to understand what is going on when the real data comes through. This paper discusses synthesized observations and how to interpret the true VLBI data when it becomes available in early 2015.

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1 Introduction

Since their discovery, black holes have captured the imagination of the public, novelists, film makers and scientists alike. They are great unknowns with physical properties that are unlike anything we experience. Sagittarius A*, situated at the center of the Milky Way is the closest and largest black hole to Earth. Its proximity and relatively large angular diameter provides scientists with the opportunity to look more closely at black hole dynamics.

1.1 Sagittarius A*

The compact radio source, Sagittarius A*, was first detected in 1974 by Bruce Balick and Robert Brown using the NRAO baseline interferometer (Goss, Brown and Lo, 2003). Located in the Sagittarius constellation, its name was denoted with an asterisk to indicate that it was an exciting finding, mimicking the style of chemists who use asterisks to denote electrons in excited states. Not long after its discovery, in the early 1980s, the first dynamical evidence for a central mass emerged (Genzel, Eisenhauer and Gillessen, 2010). A group at University of California, Berkeley took the radial velocities of ionized gas in the central parsec around Sgr A* and discovered velocities of a few hundred km/s, suggesting a central mass of 2 - 4 million solar masses. The group concluded that the compact source might plausibly be a massive black hole (Lacy et al., 1980, Lacy, Townes Hollenbach 1982). However, not everyone was convinced because gravity is not the only force affecting the dynamics of ionized gas.

In the 1990s, stellar velocity dispersion measurements provided more concrete evidence. Stellar proper motions measured within the central few arcseconds showed a very clear Keplerian motion and put much doubt to rest that the stars were in fact orbiting a very large compact mass (Genzel, Eisenhauer and Gillessen, 2010). Diffraction-limited imaging with the Keck 10m telescope to measure the proper motion of stars around the galactic core in 1998 also set constraints on the mass of the central object to within an order of magnitude of $10^6 M_\odot$ (Ghez et al., 1998). VLBI techniques were used over a period of 8 years which further constrained the mass parameter to $4 * 10^6 M_\odot$ and the intrinsic size within 1 AU implying a density of $10^{22} M_\odot pc^{-1}$ (Reid and Brunthaler, 2004).

1.2 Interferometry and VLBI

Interferometry is the process of collecting light from one source over an array of antennas and collating the signal to produce an image. The linked array simulates a larger telescope with a diameter equal to the distance between pairs of antennas. Thus, with increased diameter, the image produced is of higher angular resolution than could be produced by any single antenna in the array. Angular resolution can also be improved by decreasing the wavelength being observed.

Very Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) is a special case in which antennas are spaced across the world. The separation of antennas is limited by the size of the Earth and resolution becomes wavelength dependent. Limitations exist on how small our observing wavelengths can be and are discussed below. Major factors considered, VLBI favors light in the radio spectrum which can be coherently recorded to disk. Work is currently being done to improve millimeter and sub-millimeter VLBI which is the most promising technique for analyzing compact radio sources such as Sgr A*. There exists a realistic expectation that VLBI techniques will soon make imaging the event horizon of Sgr A* possible (Falcke, Melia and Agol, 2000).

Signal collation must take into account the geometry of the array and its posi-

tion on our rotating planet. With antennas separated by distances much larger than a single wavelength, the light emitted from the source in one instant will reach the Earth and hit each antenna at a different time. These signals are considered to be 'out of phase' with one another. To produce an accurate image of the source, phase must be corrected for.

Data collected contains time-stamp information about arrival of photons which is then used to make phase corrections. Time data is limited by the accuracy of the antenna's clock. Thus, while it would be ideal to use very small, high-energy wavelengths to observe, they require time stamp accuracy beyond our current capability and would introduce phase error. Commonly employed techniques rely on the assumption that all calibration errors 'close', or cancel, when computed over closed loops of VLBI baselines (Fish and Doeleman, 2009). In most cases, closure is possible and so we will adopt this assumption for simplicity.

Each antenna also introduces its own instrumental gain. Especially relevant for VLBI, varying sky and atmospheric conditions between the antennas contribute to this complex gain term, affecting the visibility amplitude. Iterative 'self calibration' is used to converge a sky brightness model with VLBI time-lapse data and the complex gains for each site (Cornwell Wilkinson, 1981).

1.3 The Event Horizon Telescope

The most recent and ongoing project in VLBI is the Event Horizon Telescope, a worldwide network of radio telescopes. Due to the wide dispersion of the telescope units, EHT will effectively simulate an 'earth-sized telescope' by using interferometry to link radio antennas from across the globe to make sub-millimeter observations of Sgr A*. Differentiating EHT from projects that came before it, EHT observes at 1.3mm, making it the most promising project for high angular resolution analysis of Sgr A*.

1.3.1 Sites

The EHT is comprised of already existing Radio telescopes around the world. This both minimizes cost and time in building the infrastructure for the project. There are currently three sites online, with a fourth and fifth to be added in early 2015.

Increasing the number of sites in the network increases the number of baselines as $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$, where n is the number of units in the network. With antennas located at various distances from each other across the globe, we have the opportunity to observe Sgr A* on a diversity of baseline lengths. VLBI also uses the rotation of the Earth to sample different baselines.

1.3.2 Observing and Signal to Noise

To estimate the signal-to-noise of the EHT, we use the scan length, observing bandwidth and a "system-equivalent flux density" (SEFD) for each site.

Site List			
Site Name	Location	Effective Diameter	SEFD _{230GHz}
		[m]	[Jy]
ALMA	Atacama, Chile	85	110
CARMA	California, USA	27	3500
LMT	Sierra Negra, Mexico	50	560
SMT	Arizona, USA	10	11900
SMA	Mauna Kea, Hawaii	23	4900
SPT	South Pole	AND	1000*

*SPT is currently being deployed and hence the true SEFD is not yet available.

The signal is the amplitude of visibility along a baseline. The noise on the same baseline can be approximated as

$$\sqrt{\frac{SEFD_1 * SEFD_2}{bandwidth * time}}$$

To make estimates about the integration time for observations with a bandwidth of 1 GHz, we will look at the CARMA-SMA baseline which has a signal amplitude of 0.5 Jy. The noise for this baseline is $\sqrt{(3500Jy * 4900Jy)/(10^9 Hz * time)}$ and so, for a signal-to-noise ratio of 1, we set noise=0.5 Jy, giving an integration time of 0.069s. For the same baseline, a reasonable observing s-n ratio of 20 would then be reached after 27.44s.

1.3.3 Operation Goals

The primary goals of this group are threefold; testing general relativity in the strong field regime, understanding accretion around a black hole and understanding jet genesis and collimation. The work in this paper will deal with only the second of the three goals.

An additional motivating goal of the EHT is to directly image the "shadow" of Sagittarius A*. The "shadow" is a predicted observable with an apparent diameter of 10 gravitational radii and is cast by the Event Horizon due to strong gravitational lensing near the black hole [shadow of the black hole reference]. Event horizons are a defining characteristic of black holes and imaging the shadow cast by the Event Horizon of Sgr A* would be considered unambiguous evidence for the presence of a black hole. The shadow has a predicted size of 30 μ arcseconds which, given other optimal conditions for spin and orientation, presents a realistic expectation for imaging the shadow using submillimeter VLBI. Another observable is the bright edge, known as the photon ring, that surrounds the shadow (Johannsen, 2013). The shape photon ring is determined by the geometry of the surrounding spacetime and unaffected by the accretion flow structure. This photon ring is clearly visible in the 3D-GRMHD simulation we have used for the analysis in this report (Moscibrodzka et al. 2009).

2 Method

2.1 Observing using VLBI

The correlation between the visibility in the observing plane and the Fourier transform of the image is known as the Van Cittert-Zernike theorem (Carozzi and Woan, 2009) and is given below.

$$v(\vec{u}) = \int d^2\vec{x} I(x, y) e^{-2\pi i \vec{u} \cdot \vec{x}}$$

If we could perfectly detect these photons as they arrived from the source at the same time on each radio telescope, our job would be much easier. However, due largely to instrumentation limitations and the variable atmosphere that affects each of the radio telescopes in the VLBI array differently, the information we receive in reality is a little different:

$$v'(\vec{u}) = v(\vec{u}) \cdot G \cdot e^{i\theta}$$

Here $e^{i\theta}$ and G refer to the complex phase and gain terms, respectively, that are introduced by instrumentation and atmosphere. They appear in our equations in this form because the values are unique to each station. The effect of these terms is to augment the intrinsic amplitude and phase of the signal. The Closure Phase and Amplitude processes below describe how to correct for phase and amplitude, respectively. which must be corrected for to produce a true image. Given that v is measure along the baseline between units, we can therefore define the following:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{jk} &= [E_1 E_2^*] \\ G_{jk} &= G_j G_k \\ \theta_{jk} &= \theta_j - \theta_k \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Closure Phase

We can convince ourselves that with three units in our array, and therefore 3 baselines which form a triangle, we can eliminate the effect of varying phase between the baselines by multiplying the received signal along each baseline. This is the *closure phase*

$$v'_{12}v'_{23}v'_{31} = v_{12}v_{23}v_{31} \cdot G_{12}G_{23}G_{31} \cdot e^{i(\theta_{12}+\theta_{23}+\theta_{31})}$$

Where $e^{\theta_{12}+\theta_{23}+\theta_{31}} = e^{\theta_1-\theta_2+\theta_2-\theta_3+\theta_3-\theta_1} = e^{i0}$, and setting $A = G_{12}G_{23}G_{31}$, we get

$$v'_{12}v'_{23}v'_{31} = A \cdot v_{12}v_{23}v_{31}$$

Here, the phase has been corrected for, however the G terms that remain suggest that we get a amplitude values that are some complex multiple of the true signal.

2.3 Closure Amplitude

To eliminate the amplitude variation, we must perform another operation. This operation requires four baselines and therefore a four-unit array. This is the *closure amplitude*.

$$\left| \frac{v'_{12}v'_{34}}{v'_{13}v'_{24}} \right| = \left| \frac{v_{12}v_{34}G_{12}G_{34}e^{i(\theta_{12}+\theta_{34})}}{v_{13}v_{24}G_{13}G_{24}e^{i(\theta_{13}+\theta_{24})}} \right|$$

Where $G_{12}G_{34} = G_1G_2G_3G_4$ and $G_{13}G_{24} = G_1G_3G_2G_4$, which reduces to a factor of 1. Here, the amplitude has been corrected for however the e^θ terms that remain suggest that our phase is not the correct phase of the true signal.

2.4 Simulating VLBI Observations with Movie Models

In this paper, we use time-variable, ray-traced, GRMHD (General Relativistic MagnetoHydroDynamic) movies created by Hotaka Shiokawa (Moscibrodzka et al., 2009) with frames that span 200s each. This time-resolution that may limit our ability to detect source information on well-defined timescales for black hole. Namely, each frame represents ten gravitational timescales which are 20 seconds each and can be computed using $G * M/c^3$.

The movies show Sgr A* evolve as a dynamic 'fluid' of hot magnetized plasma in the spacetime near the black hole at 230 GHz (Moscibrodzka et al., 2012). We were provided with movies at two different accretion rates, one at the current "best bet" accretion rate (Moscibrodzka et al., 2009). and the other at

a factor of 8 greater. The best bet model was developed by fitting simulation outputs with the observed spectrum of Sgr A* at different frequencies. We have access to models at two different inclinations, 45° and 85°. Here, inclination is defined as the angle between the angular momentum of the accretion disk and the line of sight of the Earth. In Shiokawa's models, the black hole spin axis is aligned with the axis of the angular momentum of the accretion disk however alternative cases may also be true.

Using Mathematica, we have developed a method to process the movies and produce VLBI-like data. Each frame is imported and mapped onto a 256x265 array where each pixel represents 1.23 μ as on the sky and is assigned a value for flux density.

2.5 Characterizing the Baseline Tracks

To account for the rotation of the Earth, we use the geocentric cartesian coordinate system, where the x-axis is along the line from the center of the earth to the intersection of the equator and prime meridian. Each telescope site is given a coordinate position in wavelengths where $\lambda = 1.3mm$. A baseline is therefore a vector between two sites.

We define SGRavec as a vector directed at Sagittarius A* when it is directly above the prime meridian. SGRavec is then crossed with the baseline vectors. To determine a baseline track as Earth rotates, we take the projection of this cross product onto vector (0,0,1). The tracks are cut when Sag A* is less than 15 degrees in altitude to account for the practical difficulty of imaging objects close to the horizon.

For the remainder of this work, I will denote the baselines in each by B1 through B4, where B1 is the shortest and B4 is the longest. For simplicity, I have elected to use a fixed B1 and B2. B1 is the very short baseline between the furthest detectors within the CARMA array. B2 is the baseline that runs between SMT and CARMA.

I've chosen 4 additional detectors, located at increasing distances from SMT and CARMA, that will provide us with a series of different baseline lengths for observation. They are, respectively, LMT, SMA, ALMA and SPT. The tracks for each of the four arrays are shown in Figure 1, below.

In Figure 2, the same tracks are co-plotted to more clearly display the baseline coverage as the Earth rotates. From these plots, LMT and SMA are present in the region between the inner and outermost tracks. These baselines are important in that they will be sampling the intermediate range, where the difference between a Gaussian model and a ring model are most evident, allowing further constraints to be made on current models.

Figure 1: Baseline tracks plotted over 24 hours. Top left: LMT-SMT-CARMA, top right: SMA-SMT-CARMA, bottom left: ALMA-SMT-CARMA, bottom right: SPT-SMT-CARMA.

3 Results

The results discussed in this report pertain only to the closure amplitude calculations. As introduced in Section 2.3, closure amplitude is the interferometric technique used to correct for the excess gain term, G , introduced by the instrument and atmospheric conditions.

3.1 Closure Amplitude Plots

The closure amplitudes of all four simulations have been taken on each of the four arrays introduced in Section 2.5. They are displayed in Figure 3.

3.2 Closure Amplitude, Static-Earth and Static-Source

There are two factors contributing to the variation in data that we see in the closure amplitude plots. The first is variation in the source itself and the second is the Earth's rotation. To ensure that the data we are looking at is significant

Figure 2: Baseline tracks plotted over 24 hours for SMA, SMT, LMT, CARMA, SPT and ALMA.

and representative of Sgr A*'s dynamics, we need to determine the time-scale of variation that occurs as a result of the Earth's rotation.

To resolve this question, I ran the same program with the dynamic baselines and only the first frame of the Sgr* movie to create a source-static curve. Similarly, I then ran the program with with the dynamic movie on a fixed baseline to create an Earth-static curve. In Figure 3 I've plotted the original closure phase data against the static-source data and static-Earth.

4 Analysis

4.1 Graphical Analysis

4.1.1 Closure Amplitude

The shortest two baselines of the set, B1 and B2 have much lower resolution than the other baselines and see only coarse details across a larger section of the source. If we had a small, point-like source, we would expect B1 and B2 to

Figure 3: Closure amplitude plots (mustard) against B1/B2 (blue) and B4/B3 (purple). The red line is set at one to provide a reference. The first column displays the simulated plots for the LMT-SMT-CARMA array, followed by SMA-SMT-CARMA, ALMA-SMT-CARMA and SPT-SMT-CARMA in the second, third and fourth columns, respectively. The first and second rows display the plots for the model with Sgr A* oriented at 45° with a mass accretion rate 1 and 8 times the best best bet accretion flow, respectively. The third and fourth rows display the plots for each array with Sgr A* oriented at 85° with a mass accretion rate of 1 and 8 times the best best bet accretion flow, respectively.

observe the same visibility because neither are able to resolve fine detail, giving B1/B2 1. If, however, it's a much bigger source, B2 may be able to resolve some detail that B1 cannot, in which case we could expect $B1/B2 > 1$. We can use this understanding to draw information about the size of Sgr A* from closure amplitude data if there is an observable distinction between models of different accretion rates. We used our models to determine the observability of changes in mass accretion rate on the B1/B2 ratio.

In our plots with an accretion rate of $\dot{M} = 1$, B1/B2 is linear averages out at around 1, as expected for a small source. When the accretion rate is increased to $\dot{M} = 8$, we see B1/B2 2 and again linear. As discussed above, we expect the B1/B2 value to increase for larger objects. Given more films with intermediate mass accretion rates, we could better map out the B1/B2 average value for different \dot{M} values and use this to constrain the mass accretion.

Figure 4: Closure amplitude (mustard) for the SMA-SMT-CARMA array plotted against the static-source data (in purple) and static-Earth (in blue). Red line is given as a reference at $V=1$. Top left: 45° inclined with best bet model mass accretion rate, bottom left: 45° inclined with 8 times best bet model mass accretion rate. Top right: 85° inclined with best bet model mass accretion rate, bottom right: 85° inclined with 8 times best bet model mass accretion rate. These closure amplitude plots are shown in the second column of Figure 3.

The $B4/B3$ quotient contains information about the source at higher angular resolutions and therefore may show smaller scale fluctuations. If $B4/B3 \approx 1$, then on those baselines, the source is behaving like a gaussian distribution. Where $B4/B3 \neq 1$, indicates the presence of a "ringing" structure in the visibilities. This may reflect sharp edges in the image, such as that which would be produced by the black hole shadow.

Looking across the 16 plots from left to right, there is clearly more variation occurring on the longer baselines which indicates that the fluctuations are on smaller scales and require high angular resolution to be observed. There is generally also greater fluctuation in the models with a mass accretion rate that is 8 times the best bet model value. This is to be expected. Given that it is unlikely that the true mass accretion rate of Sgr A* is as much as 8 times the best bet value, a concern is that the amplitude of fluctuations will be too small to detect even on the longest baselines. However, the plot for the 45° and $\dot{M} = 1$ model on the ALMA-SMT-CARMA and SPT-SMT-CARMA baselines shows promise for closure amplitude observables.

4.1.2 Closure Amplitude, Static-Earth and Static-Source

From Figure 4, the timescale of fluctuations caused by the Earth’s rotation on a single frame from the movie is much longer than that of the fluctuations . These timescales could be better constrained by Fourier analysis, however by eye alone we can see that major fluctuations in the closure amplitude are from the source and that it is easily distinguishable from Earth-rotational effects.

4.2 Timescale Analysis

4.2.1 Visual Analysis

Of the four arrays we produced closure amplitude curves for, it is clear by observation that the SPT-SMT-CARMA array gives the greatest amplitude fluctuations. Looking at the peaks on the plot for the 45° and $\dot{M} = 8$ model, there is some obvious periodicity. The horizontal axis here is given in frame numbers and each frame represents 3 minutes.

Figure 5: Plot of the simulated 45° and $\dot{M} = 8$ model on the SPT-SMT-CARMA array. Green circles highlight periodicity.

The highlighted features span 14 frames each which is equivalent to 47 mins. Between the two features, there is a separation of 34 frames, corresponding to 106 mins. Individual peaks span approximately 2 frames, or 7 mins, each.

While approximate, these values give us a sense of the timescales on which we can expect to see activity for the model. To improve our results, we can perform Fourier analysis on these plots. The objective of Fourier analysis is to decompose the different frequency sinusoids and their respective amplitudes that combine to form the waveform being analyzed. Therefore, we can use this method to characterize the closure amplitude data and accurately extract the timescale for fluctuations.

4.2.2 Physical Timescales

It is also important to consider the physical time scales associated with the black hole itself. To ensure that our results are significant, we must confirm that the timescale for variations in our data does not align with physical timescales. If it does align, then it is possible that our results will be masking significant results.

There are three physical timescales to take into account. The first is the gravitational timescale. It can be described as the light-crossing time of the gravitational radius which is equal to half the Schwarzschild radius ($r_s = 2GM/c^2$). The gravitational timescale is then

$$t_g = \frac{GM}{c^3}$$

Taking the mass of Sag A* to be $4.1 * 10^6 M_\odot$ as discussed in section 1.1, we get a value of t_g 20s. Given that our frames have a timescale of 200s, we are only getting a look at one in every ten gravitational times.

The second of the timescales is that of the orbit around a black hole. There are two orbits that we are interested in; the photon orbit and the mass orbit. Photons are forced to travel in orbits in regions of space where gravity is extremely strong. The region of space containing these orbits is known as the photon sphere. The photon sphere has a radius which is one and a half times the Schwarzschild radius and is also the lower bound for any stable orbit.

Similarly, with mass around the black hole, we are interested in the Innermost Stable Circular Orbit (ISCO) which is at the same radius as the photon sphere in the case that the black hole has maximal spin (Hod, 2014). When the spin is zero, has a radius equal to twice the radius of the photon sphere. The ISCO time scale depends upon the spin of the black hole, a . The spin of Sagittarius A* is currently not well defined. If maximally spinning, t_{ISCO} 10mins (Dexter et al., 2014).

The third and final timescale we should consider is called the viscous timescale. It describes how long it takes for matter to fall onto the black hole. We define 'falling into the black hole' as being within the Bondi radius. This timescale depends upon the turbulence and viscosity of the flow. This timescale is much larger than the previous two, therefore it is unlikely to pose any problems for our analysis. However, we are limited again by our simulations which only extend out as far as a few tens of Schwarzschild radii and bear no information about inflow on longer timescales.

5 Discussion

5.1 Summary of important results

Over the course of the semester, I have analyzed the closure amplitude for accretion rates of 1 and 8 times the best bet value at 45° and 85° inclination to our line of sight.

Looking at simulated data in the Earth-static and source-static cases, we were able to determine that the dominant amplitude fluctuations in both high-accretion and low-accretion models at 45° and 85° inclination is due to activity from the source, not the Earth's rotation.

If the GRMHD model is correct, there is closure amplitude variability on small scales. Therefore to make any conclusions about the feasibility of this model, we must make real closure amplitude measurements with long baselines that have sufficient angular resolution to resolve the small structures we see in our plots.

There is clear periodicity in the plots produced for closure amplitude. Closure amplitude periodicity on the scale of 70 minutes may have some significance in the dynamics of Sgr A* and it would be interesting to explore how this timescale changes with movies built on slightly different parameters. This timescale provides us with another observable with which we can compare real data.

5.2 Future Work

The results in this report demonstrate that our models have potential to constrain important parameters in the real data that will be collected in early 2015. However, to prepare for this data, we would benefit from sampling a range of models with varying accretion rates. Knowing the correlation between the average B1/B2 value and the \dot{M} value will allow us to determine the mass accretion rate in the real data.

Fourier analysis of the time scales for variation in closure amplitude is an obvious next step to better constrain the periodicity of observable fluctuations. To determine whether these timescales are significant, we need to ensure that they are characteristic rather than situational. By this I mean, we need to be sure that the fluctuations we observed in the first 70 frames of the movies are of the same nature as the fluctuations over any 70-frame period of time in the movie. This analysis could be performed by looking at alternative segments of the data and performing Fourier analysis to check for consistency.

Additionally, it would be valuable to do Fourier analysis on the amplitude variations caused by Earth's rotation alone. This would also allow us to subtract out the effects of this rotation and look at the source-only variation.

We are also interested in running these simulations to produce plots for closure phase. This work was started this semester but was omitted from this report as results were inconclusive.

5.3 Conclusions

This work prepares us for future analysis of real closure amplitude data. Using plots generated from movies models, as has been demonstrated in this report, proves to be an effective way to make constraints on parameters of interest and develop a sense of the familiarity with the form of the closure amplitude plots we might expect to get from observations of Sgr A*.

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